

On Idealized Models of Turbulent Condensation in Clouds

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ABSTRACT: Various microphysical models attempt to explain the occurrence of broad droplet size distributions (DSDs) in clouds through approximate representations of the stochastic droplet growth by condensation in a turbulent environment. This work analyzes specific idealized models, where the variability of droplet growth conditions arises primarily from variability in the turbulent vertical velocity of the air carrying these droplets. Examples are the stochastic eddy-hopping model operating in adiabatic parcels and certain types of direct numerical simulation (DNS)-like models. We show that such models produce droplet size statistics that are spatially inhomogeneous along the vertical direction, causing the predicted DSD to depend on the DSD spatial sampling scale Δ . In these models, Δ is implicitly related to the spatial extent of the droplet turbulent diffusion (approximated by Brownian-like excursions) and thus grows like $t^{1/2}$. This leads to spurious continuous DSD broadening, as the growth in time (also like $t^{1/2}$) of the standard deviation of droplet squared radius arises essentially from the growth of the sampling scale Δ . Also, the DSDs predicted by the models discussed here are *nonlocally* broad (in the sense that large and small droplets are not well mixed in sufficiently small volumes) and thus do not necessarily indicate enhanced probabilities of gravity-induced droplet coagulation. In the effort to build a firm physical basis for subgrid parameterizations, this study presents a framework to explain the merits and limitations of idealized models, indicating how to assess and use them wisely as a subgrid representation of turbulent condensation in large-eddy simulations of clouds.

SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT: The droplet size distribution is a prime characteristic of a cloud, controlling the initiation of precipitation and how the cloud modulates solar radiation. Microphysical processes shaping the droplet size distribution, such as droplet growth by condensation in the turbulent cloud flow, occur on scales that are small compared with the resolution of the numerical models used to simulate the entire cloud. Such subgrid-scale aspects are incorporated in these models by parameterizations relating microphysical processes to the model variables. In the effort to build a firm physical basis for such parameterizations, this study analyzes idealized representations of turbulent condensation at subgrid-scales and presents a framework to explain the merits and limitations of these representations, indicating how to overcome their deficiencies.

KEYWORDS: Turbulence; Cloud microphysics; Drop size distribution; Stochastic models; Subgrid-scale processes

1. Introduction

Adiabatic cloud parcel models and direct numerical simulations (DNSs) of cloudy volumes with triply periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) are widely used frameworks to study cloud microphysics. These idealized frameworks are designed to provide a basic understanding of cloud processes occurring at small scales and eventually give insights into the central problem of subgrid-scale (SGS) modeling of cloud microphysics in large-eddy simulations (LESs) of clouds.

The suitability of these idealized models to explain, in particular, the occurrence of local broad droplet size distributions in clouds has been recently questioned by Prabhakaran et al. (2022). Their objections concern models where the variability of droplet growth conditions (determined by the supersaturation droplet experience) is due primarily to the variability of the turbulent vertical velocity of the air carrying these droplets (through the adiabatic cooling effect). Examples of

such models are the so-called eddy-hopping model¹ (e.g., Sardina et al. 2015; Grabowski and Abade 2017; Abade et al. 2018) operating in adiabatic cloud parcels and a certain type of DNS-like model (e.g., Vaillancourt et al. 2002; Celani et al. 2005, 2008, 2009; Lanotte et al. 2009; Sardina et al. 2015, 2018; Saito and Gotoh 2018; Thomas et al. 2020; Grabowski et al. 2022b,a).

The models mentioned above presumably predict broad droplet size distributions, in general qualitative agreement with in situ measurements. However, as we shall explain later, the predicted droplet size distributions are dependent on the sampling volume (which is generally unspecified) and (as pointed out by Prabhakaran et al. 2022) cannot be generally regarded as *locally* broad. That is, large and small droplets, forming the left and right tails of the predicted distribution, might not be well mixed in sufficiently small cloudy volumes. This feature is important because locally broad droplet size

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¹ The term “eddy hopping” to identify the mechanism underlying these idealized models was initiated by Grabowski and Abade (2017) and repeatedly used in subsequent works. Due to the lack of a better naming, we keep using this terminology here as well, but note that this is inadequate and may lead to misconceptions (see discussion in section 9).

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distributions accelerate the onset of the collision–coalescence process, as they enhance the probability of gravity-induced droplet collision due to differential sedimentation velocities of droplets having different sizes.

Idealized adiabatic cloud parcels and cloudy periodic boxes in DNS models, combined with some explicit treatment of the microphysics, are commonly regarded as instrumental models to represent the unresolved subgrid cloudy states in LES. This is based on the picture that the subgrid microphysical state of a particular grid box (of linear size Δ) consists of a statistical ensemble of the microphysical states of adiabatic parcels or DNS periodic boxes (of characteristic size Δ) that instantaneously occupy the volume of this particular grid box. In this picture, there are two essential aspects associated with the characteristic size Δ : (i) This is generally the scale on which the cloudy air in a grid box is assumed to acquire its mean turbulent kinetic energy k at the rate ε per unit mass and (ii) it specifies the linear extent of the *sampling volume* over which relevant microphysical characteristics, such as the droplet size distribution and its moments, are evaluated. One way to state a central issue we bring out in this paper is that the eddy-hopping model and some DNS-like studies observe only the first aspect (i), that is, Δ as the scale on which turbulent kinetic energy is supplied to the system, but inadvertently miss the second essential aspect (ii), that Δ also specifies the extent of the averaging volume. This omission results in implicit *non-local* sampling of microphysical properties and arises from ill-suited boundary conditions, as we shall clarify later in this work. Issues with ill-suited boundary conditions used in these idealized models were indicated by Prabhakaran et al. (2022).

This work describes a framework to explain the deficiencies and merits of the idealized models of turbulent condensation mentioned above. The suggested framework addresses the specific comments of Prabhakaran et al. (2022) (see their section 5b) and assists us in properly sampling the droplet size statistics in idealized models, as we shall do for the eddy-hopping model operating in adiabatic cloud parcels. In particular, understanding the deficiencies and merits of the eddy-hopping model (as a stand-alone representation of turbulent condensation in adiabatic parcels) will motivate its wise use as a subgrid condensation model built in an LES scheme that employs particle-based microphysics. We also formulate a consistency condition for any subgrid model of turbulent condensation that (explicitly or not) includes turbulent vertical velocity fluctuations as one possible source of subgrid supersaturation variability.

Before we proceed with this program, some preliminary background is provided in section 2, where we define the droplet size distribution (DSD) and discuss its dependence on the sampling volume. For clarity, we outline in section 3 the theoretical framework of Cooper (1989), which is based on the quasisteady supersaturation approximation, and recall the *reversible condensation* scenario. This is a useful reference scenario where no strictly local DSD broadening is possible. The framework of Cooper (1989) incorporates many previous explanations (e.g., Bartlett and Jonas 1972; Manton 1979) of the flaws in earlier versions of the stochastic condensation theory, which was revised and improved by Khvorostyanov and Curry (1999). In section 4, we recall the essentials of the

eddy-hopping model operating in adiabatic parcels, explain its deficiencies, and propose ways to enforce a correct *local sampling* of the DSD. Section 5 discusses deviations from the quasisteady approximation and explores insights from the work of Clark and Hall (1979) on possible ways in which DSD may become locally broad. Section 6 briefly reviews two types of DNS-like studies of turbulent condensation and explains that one of these types has the same deficiencies as the eddy-hopping model. Section 7 discusses the effects of sedimentation and droplet inertia. In section 8, we discuss some aspects that emerge when idealized stochastic models (in particular, the eddy hopping model) are used as a subgrid condensation scheme in LES of clouds with particle-based microphysics. In section 9, we summarize the main points of this work.

2. Fine-grained and filtered DSD

The fundamental characteristic of a cloudy volume considered in this work is the DSD. Because it may depend on the volume over which the distribution is averaged, every well-defined DSD goes with the specification of its underlying spatial averaging scale.

Here, we define the *strictly local* or fine-grained DSD $n(r; \mathbf{x}, t)$ in such a way that

$$n(r; \mathbf{x}, t) d\mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

is the number of droplets that lie in the volume element $d\mathbf{x}$ around \mathbf{x} at time t and that have a radius in the range $[r, r + dr]$. This definition implicitly incorporates the *continuum hypothesis* for the dispersed liquid phase in the cloudy air. Thus, *local* refers to the mathematically infinitesimal volume element $d\mathbf{x}$ of a particular “physical point” in the continuous cloud. This physical point is assumed to be “macroscopically infinitesimal,” but at the same time “mesoscopically infinite” [following analogous considerations by Résibois and De Leener (1977) while defining regular distribution functions used in the kinetic theory of gases]. This means that such a physical point is small enough for all microphysical properties of the cloudy air not to vary appreciably over the extension of the sampling volume $d\mathbf{x}$ but at the same time big enough to contain a large number of droplets.

The fine-grained DSD discussed above is thus the local size distribution in a continuous description of cloudy air. However, the continuous equations of cloudy air motion are intractable except by numerical methods. These methods require spatial discretization that naturally introduces a cutoff length scale Δ determining the finite spatial resolution of the numerical model. In an LES setting, Δ may be loosely identified with the size of the computational grid box. A grid box is considered a “point” in the spatially discretized LES domain. Thus, the “local” DSD at this “grid point” is actually a spatially filtered DSD:

$$\langle n(r; \mathbf{x}, t) \rangle_{\Delta} = \int G(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') n(r; \mathbf{x}', t) d\mathbf{x}', \quad (2)$$

where G is a spatial filter function of characteristic filter width Δ and satisfies $\int G(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = 1$ [see, e.g., Germano (1992)]. (In the limit of $\Delta \rightarrow 0$, the filter function G tends to the Dirac delta distribution.) We note that LES generally does not

define the filter function G explicitly; an implicit filter arises from the spatial discretization. Thus, the distribution $\langle n(r) \rangle_\Delta$ is simply the grid average (or the G -weighted spatial average) of the fine-grained $n(r)$, where Δ is the spatial averaging length scale. Also, we define $\mu_k = \int r^k n(r) dr$ as the k th moment of the fine-grained DSD $n(r)$ and $\langle \mu_k \rangle_\Delta = \int r^k \langle n(r) \rangle_\Delta dr$ is the corresponding moment of the filtered DSD $\langle n(r) \rangle_\Delta$ with filter width Δ . The fine-grained variance of r , we denote by $\sigma_r(0)$, is proportional to $\mu_2 - \mu_1^2$ (up to a normalization constant), and $\sigma_r(\Delta) \propto \langle \mu_2 \rangle_\Delta - \langle \mu_1 \rangle_\Delta^2$ is the filtered variance of r .

We note that the moments μ_k and $\langle \mu_k \rangle_\Delta$ are *ensemble averages*, which are averages over realizations, with the observation point being fixed. The spatial filtering specifies the sampling volume around the observation point. That is, the ensemble average we consider is *conditional*. The ensemble average at a given observation point \mathbf{x} is computed over the droplet sizes *conditional* on droplet positions being inside a given sampling volume around \mathbf{x} . This sampling volume can be (i) $d\mathbf{x}$ around \mathbf{x} (the physical point under the approximation of a continuous cloud) or (ii) a finite volume Δ^3 (the volume of the grid box) around a grid point \mathbf{x} in a simulation setting with spatial resolution Δ . The conditional sampling (i) corresponds to the fine-grained DSD, and the conditional sampling (ii) corresponds to the filtered DSD with the filter width Δ we discussed above.

Also, if Δ is large (compared to a length scale we shall define later in section 3), the grid point may no longer be considered mathematically infinitesimal as the physical point, and the filtered DSD $\langle n(r) \rangle_\Delta$ may incorporate variation due to spatial distribution of the fine-grained DSD. Thus, spatially inhomogeneous fine-grained DSDs that are locally narrow in a theoretical physical point may produce filtered DSDs that are locally broad in a computational grid point.

3. The reversible condensation regime

A useful theoretical framework to study the DSD formation was developed by Cooper (1989). His analysis incorporates the findings of earlier works (e.g., Bartlett and Jonas 1972; Manton 1979) that rule out (under certain conditions) turbulence-induced vertical velocity fluctuations as the cause of strictly local DSD broadening. For clarity, we reproduce below some essential points of Cooper (1989) and make some remarks. A general one is that theories attempting to explain DSD broadening usually do not explicitly specify the sampling volume or spatial averaging length scale Δ underlying the examined DSD. We attempt to make this clear while recalling the *statistical ensemble* specified by Cooper (1989).

We follow Cooper (1989) closely and assume that each droplet of radius squared $a = r^2$ grows according to

$$\frac{da}{dt} = 2DS(t), \tag{3}$$

where S is the supersaturation experienced by the droplet and D is the effective diffusion coefficient (here assumed constant for simplicity). Surface tension and solute effects are neglected.

Cooper (1989) then proceeds by assuming the supersaturation $S(t)$ has approached its quasisteady value S_{qs} :

$$S \approx S_{qs} \equiv A_1 \tau_{ph} w, \tag{4}$$

where w is the vertical velocity of the air parcel surrounding the droplet (A_1 depends weakly on temperature and may be considered constant to a good approximation), $\tau_{ph} = 1/(A_2 \mu_1)$ is the phase relaxation time, μ_1 is the first moment of the DSD, and A_2 is a constant. The τ_{ph} is the time constant for the exponential approach of $S(t)$ to S_{qs} and characterizes the local structure of the cloudy environment where the droplet grows. Although (4) is not valid everywhere (e.g., near the cloud base), the quasisteady regime is a useful limit for analysis.

The first moment μ_1 specifying τ_{ph} can be written as $\mu_1 = N \langle r \rangle$, where $N = \mu_0$ is the droplet number concentration (corresponding to the zeroth moment μ_0 of the DSD), and $\langle r \rangle = \mu_1/N$ is the mean droplet radius. The sampling volume underlying μ_1 and μ_0 (and hence N and $\langle r \rangle$) was not explicitly specified in Cooper (1989); thus, we assume here that μ_1 and μ_0 are moments of the fine-grained DSD defined in section 2.

The idealized models of turbulent condensation we will discuss here assume that

$$\tau_{ph} \approx \bar{\tau}_{ph} \equiv 1/[A_2 \langle \mu_1 \rangle_\Delta], \tag{5}$$

where Δ is the characteristic size of the sampling volume that includes all droplets of the ensemble.

We also assume that the droplets are suspended and follow the airflow as tracers (droplet-tracer limit). Then, the vertical component z of the droplet position is related to the velocity w by

$$dz = w(t)dt. \tag{6}$$

Hence,

$$da \approx \bar{\gamma}_a dz, \quad \bar{\gamma}_a \equiv 2DA_1 \bar{\tau}_{ph}. \tag{7}$$

Now, consider a droplet that at time t_0 has been activated with activation squared radius a_0 at the cloud base located at z_0 . Under the assumptions above, the droplet squared radius at time $t > t_0$ for a droplet located at $Z(t) > z_0$ is

$$a[Z(t)] \approx a_{rev}[Z(t)],$$

where

$$a_{rev}(z) \equiv a_0 + \bar{\gamma}_a(z - z_0) \tag{8}$$

is the *reversible* squared radius. For fixed a_0 and z_0 , (8) is a *one-to-one relation* between the droplet squared radius a and the droplet vertical position z . This defines the scenario of perfectly *reversible condensation*.²

² Consider a droplet of initial squared radius $a(t_0)$ ascending with a time-dependent vertical velocity $w(t)$ for a certain time $t_0 \leq t \leq t_1$. Now, reverse the vertical velocity by setting $w(t) = -w[2(t_1 - t_0) - t]$ in $t_1 \leq t \leq 2(t_1 - t_0)$. Under the reversible condensation regime, not only will the droplet vertical motion reverse, but also its growth history will reverse because $da \propto w(t)dt$. Hence, its squared radius returns to its starting value $a(t_0)$.

FIG. 1. Schematic representation of (a) the point ensemble ($\Delta \rightarrow 0$) and (b) the vertically extended ensemble (finite Δ) in an idealized cloud with reversible condensation. Two droplets undergoing distinct trajectories (labeled A and B) but arriving at the same particular height z will have the same radius in (a). The breadth of the resulting fine-grained DSD vanishes. If the sampling volume is extended vertically to have a thickness Δ , then at a given time t , this sampling volume may accommodate droplets arriving at different heights in the range $[z - \Delta/2, z + \Delta/2]$ and thus having different radii in (b). The broad filtered DSD (with filter width Δ) obtained under the reversible condensation regime in (b) arises from the increase in droplet size with height [(8)] over the averaging length scale Δ .

To discuss any characteristics of a droplet size distribution, we need to specify its underlying *statistical ensemble*. The ensemble used by Cooper (1989) is comprised of all droplets reaching a given height z at a particular time t after being activated at time t_0 (with squared radius a_0) while crossing the cloud base located at z_0 . Also, all droplets in the ensemble experience the same constant phase relaxation time $\bar{\tau}_{\text{ph}}$. Thus, for this ensemble, (8) implies no variability in a_{rev} at a particular height z and the variance of a_{rev} vanishes there:

$$\sigma_a^2(z, t) = \langle [a_{\text{rev}} - \langle a_{\text{rev}} \rangle]^2 \rangle = 0. \quad (9)$$

We emphasize that the angle brackets $\langle \cdot \rangle$ in (9) denote an average over the ensemble of cloud droplets all having $Z(t) = z$ at time t and having the same activation area a_0 at the same activation level z_0 .

The scenario of *reversible condensation* above is thus defined by three main assumptions: (i) quasisteady supersaturation, (ii) lack of variability in the phase relaxation time τ_{ph} among the droplets in the ensemble, and (iii) the droplets are suspended and follow the airflow as tracers (i.e., droplet inertia and sedimentation are neglected). This third assumption is not made explicit in the analysis of Cooper (1989).

This reversible condensation scenario will serve as a reference limit, where the droplet squared radius a is *maximally correlated* with its vertical position z inside the cloud. Deviations from any of the assumptions (i) to (iii) listed above will work to destroy the one-to-one relation between a and z , thus creating conditions for broadening of the local (fine-grained) DSD.

Point and extended ensembles

In Cooper's ensemble discussed above, the ensemble averaging in (9) implicitly assumes $\Delta \rightarrow 0$ as the ensemble considers droplets reaching a particular *point* (at height z) and forming the DSD there. Thus, $\sigma_a^2(z, t)$ in (9) is the fine-grained

variance $\sigma_a^2(0)$ at a physical point in the continuous cloud in the sense discussed in section 2.

Figure 1a shows the ensemble of droplets that reach a given height z at a particular time t . There, fluctuations in the updraft velocity only cannot support the broadening of the fine-grained DSD in the regime of reversible condensation.

The situation is different in a simulation setting, where the sampling volume is finite and defined by the length scale of the smallest spatial variation resolved by the model. This motivates us to extend Cooper's point ensemble by considering the droplets that at time t reach a height in the range $[z - \Delta/2, z + \Delta/2]$, where Δ is on the order of a typical vertical length-scale resolution used in LES. This ensemble is illustrated in Fig. 1b. For this extended ensemble, the broad filtered DSD (with filter width Δ) obtained in the reversible condensation scenario arises from the increase in droplet squared radius with height over the averaging length scale Δ [(8)].

In principle, any particle-based SGS model for condensation built-in LES should capture this variability in the droplet squared radius (at least under a regime of nearly reversible condensation). However, this variability is smeared out when the SGS microphysical scheme assumes all droplets in a given grid box experience the same grid-mean supersaturation $\langle S \rangle$, as this subgrid *uniform condensation* tends to narrow the filtered DSD.

It is evident that the breadth of the local filtered DSD will depend on Δ when Δ is of the same order or larger than the length scale:

$$H_a \equiv \sigma_a(0)/|\partial a_{\text{rev}}| = \sigma_a(0)/\bar{\gamma}_a, \quad (10)$$

where $\sigma_a(0)$ denotes the *fine-grained* standard deviation of the droplet squared radius (corresponding to a vanishing sampling volume or filter width $\Delta \rightarrow 0$). Then, H_a is the length scale over which the reversible squared radius a_{rev} changes by a value $\sim \sigma_a(0)$ along the vertical direction. Thus, for $\Delta \gtrsim H_a$, the filtered DSD with filter width Δ will incorporate variation

due to the spatial distribution of the fine-grained DSD and $\sigma_a(\Delta)$ will appreciably differ from $\sigma_a(0)$.

Later, in this work, we use Cooper's framework and the reference reversible condensation scenario outlined above to discuss the current limitations of two idealized frameworks, namely, the so-called eddy-hopping model operating in adiabatic parcels and certain DNS-like models, where microphysical variability is driven by local vertical velocity fluctuations.

4. Models operating in adiabatic cloud parcels

The standard theory of droplet growth by condensation in an adiabatic cloud parcel assumes uniform condensation, where all droplets in the parcel experience the same supersaturation. This approximation produces narrow DSDs in disagreement with in situ measurements of broad droplet spectra in clouds (see, e.g., [Shaw 2003](#)).

Attempts to resolve this paradox attribute the occurrence of broad droplet size spectra in clouds to the stochastic droplet growth by condensation in a turbulent environment (see, e.g., [Khvorostyanov and Curry 1999](#)). An approximate account of turbulent effects on condensation in the adiabatic cloud parcel framework was done by [Sardina et al. \(2015\)](#), [Grabowski and Abade \(2017\)](#), and [Abade et al. \(2018\)](#). These so-called eddy-hopping models use a Lagrangian (particle-based) stochastic treatment of the droplet growth and presumably predict a broad DSD.

A much earlier numerical study by [Bartlett and Jonas \(1972\)](#) attempted to account for the effects of turbulence by subjecting the adiabatic cloud parcel to a time-dependent updraft. Their study ruled out turbulence-induced vertical velocity fluctuations as the cause of strictly local DSD broadening. Then, why does the eddy-hopping model ([Sardina et al. 2015](#); [Grabowski and Abade 2017](#); [Abade et al. 2018](#)) predict broad DSDs, while [Bartlett and Jonas \(1972\)](#) do not?

The essential difference between these two approaches lies in the statistical ensemble over which the DSD is sampled. The ensemble in [Bartlett and Jonas \(1972\)](#) corresponds to the point ensemble ([Fig. 1a](#)) with an infinitesimal sampling length scale ($\Delta \rightarrow 0$) and thus provides the *fine-grained* DSD. In contrast, the eddy-hopping model considers the extended ensemble ([Fig. 1b](#)) with a finite sampling length scale and thus provides the *filtered* DSD with filter width $\Delta \approx H_a$. While the fine-grained DSD of [Bartlett and Jonas \(1972\)](#) is narrow, the filtered DSD predicted by the eddy-hopping model is broad.

Next, we discuss the eddy-hopping model in more detail and explain a major artifact in [Sardina et al. \(2015\)](#), [Grabowski and Abade \(2017\)](#), and [Abade et al. \(2018\)](#). This artifact makes the variance of the filtered DSD in the adiabatic parcel to continuously grow in time. We show that this growth does not reflect an actual local DSD broadening with time but results from the growth in time of the filter width Δ underlying the examined DSD.

a. Eddy-hopping model and nonlocal DSD sampling

The eddy-hopping model considers an ensemble of representative cloud droplets. The model describes the evolution of four variables attached to each droplet: its squared radius a , the supersaturation S the droplet experiences, its vertical

position z , and its vertical velocity w . The evolution of the state variables (a, S, w, z) is described by the following set of equations:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = 2DS, \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -\frac{S}{\tau_s} + A_1 w, \quad (12)$$

$$dw = -\frac{w}{\tau_w} dt + \sqrt{\frac{2\sigma_w^2}{\tau_w}} dW(t), \quad (13)$$

$$dz = w dt. \quad (14)$$

The equations above include a set of model parameters $(\tau_s, \tau_w, \sigma_w)$ we shall specify later.

The identifying feature of the eddy-hopping model is that the supersaturation evolving according to (12) is forced by vertical velocity w via the adiabatic cooling of the ascending air surrounding the cloud droplet. The vertical velocity w is described by (13), where τ_w is the Lagrangian integral time scale of w and $dW(t)$ is the increment of a Wiener process (see, e.g., [Rodean 1996](#)). The latter introduces the "noise" due to turbulent fluctuations.

Equation (13) serves as a coarse representation of the vertical velocity fluctuations of a fluid particle due to a range of homogeneous isotropic turbulence eddies of sizes smaller than a characteristic length Δ . This is the length scale on which the cloud parcel, filled with homogeneous turbulence, is imagined to acquire its mean turbulent kinetic energy $k (= 3\sigma_w^2/2)$ at a given rate ε per unit mass.

Assuming that turbulent cloud parcels may provide insights into subgrid modeling of the microphysics in LESs of clouds, it is reasonable to assume that Δ has the size of a typical LES grid box. Thus, Δ lies in the inertial range of cloud turbulence and usually varies from several meters to several tens of meters.

Equation (12) for the supersaturation may be cast into the form

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -\frac{S - S_{qs}}{\tau_s}, \quad (15)$$

to make it explicit that S relaxes to the quasisteady value $S_{qs} = A_1 \tau_s w$ with a time constant τ_s —the supersaturation relaxation time. The time constant τ_s is a model parameter defined as the harmonic mean of the phase relaxation time τ_{ph} and the relaxation time τ_{mix} associated with turbulent mixing $\tau_s = 1/(\tau_{ph}^{-1} + \tau_{mix}^{-1})$. We commonly assume $\tau_{mix} \approx \tau_w$.

For times sufficiently longer than τ_s , the supersaturation has attained its quasisteady value $S \approx S_{qs}$ which is proportional to $w(t)$ [as in (4)]. Then, it follows from (14) that the increment da in the droplet squared radius is closely related to the increment dz in its vertical position:

$$da \approx \bar{\gamma}_a dz, \quad (16)$$

where $\bar{\gamma}_a = 2DA_1 \tau_s$ and we have assumed that τ_s is the same for all representative droplets in the ensemble.

FIG. 2. (a) Nonlocal sampling in a turbulent adiabatic parcel, where the linear extent $\tilde{\Delta}(t)$ of the implicit sampling volume grows like $\sim t^{1/2}$ due to turbulent diffusion of cloud particles in all directions. As time increases, $\tilde{\Delta}(t)$ becomes larger than the characteristic length scale Δ on which the parcel acquires its turbulent kinetic energy. The same problem occurs in DNS-like models with usual PBCs in the vertical direction (see discussion in section 6). (b) Adiabatic parcel with DSD statistics sampled over a subensemble of droplets (gray) using proper boundary conditions at the top and bottom to enforce local sampling (see text for details).

Also, it follows from (13) and (14) that (for times sufficiently longer than τ_w) the mean squared displacement along the vertical direction grows (see, e.g., Lemons 2002) like

$$\langle [z(t) - \langle z \rangle]^2 \rangle \sim t, \quad (17)$$

being the average $\langle \dots \rangle$ calculated over all the representative cloud droplets. Thus, the relation (16) implies that the variance σ_a^2 of droplet squared radius grows according to the same scaling:

$$\sigma_a^2 = \langle [a(t) - \langle a \rangle]^2 \rangle \sim t, \quad (18)$$

when the average is computed over the same ensemble of representative droplets.

In conclusion, the eddy-hopping model predicts continuous DSD broadening as the variance σ_a^2 grows with time (Sardina et al. 2015). However, this broadening is *nonlocal* in a sense to be explained soon below. This nonlocal feature underlying the continuous growth of σ_a was overlooked by Sardina et al. (2015), Grabowski and Abade (2017), and Abade et al. (2018) because they inadvertently omitted (14) from their description.

The fluctuating vertical velocity w that drives supersaturation fluctuations S also drives the vertical dispersion of cloud particles. The spatial extent of this droplet dispersion is measured by the mean squared displacement [(17)]. Thus, the associated length scale is

$$\tilde{\Delta}(t) = \langle [z(t) - \langle z \rangle]^2 \rangle^{1/2} \sim t^{1/2}, \quad (19)$$

which may be understood as the linear size of the sampling volume containing the whole droplet population in the parcel grows with the square root of time. The sampling length scale $\tilde{\Delta}(t)$ is not bounded and may eventually exceed the fixed scale Δ on which energy is assumed to be supplied to the turbulence filling the parcel. We refer to this as the implicit *nonlocal*

sampling of the DSD in the eddy-hopping model, which is illustrated schematically in Fig. 2a. Figure 3 shows numerical results for the continuous droplet dispersion along the vertical extrapolating Δ (gray dots in Figs. 3a and 3b) and the corresponding continuous growth of the standard deviation $\sigma_a[\tilde{\Delta}(t)]$ (gray line in Fig. 3c).

b. Enforcing local sampling of the DSD

For the eddy-hopping model to be relevant as an SGS stochastic condensation scheme in LES, then $\tilde{\Delta}$ (the linear extent of the volume over which droplet size statistics is sampled) should be bounded to Δ . This ensures a well-defined filtered variance $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$ that refers to the droplet population inside a grid box of size Δ . This motivates us to enforce local sampling of the DSD in the adiabatic parcel and DNS-like frameworks as well.

We consider three different ways of imposing local DSD sampling depending on the framework where the eddy-hopping model operates.

First, we may sample the droplet size statistics over a *subensemble* of cloud particles all having vertical position $Z(t)$ between $\langle z \rangle - \Delta/2$ and $\langle z \rangle + \Delta/2$, as illustrated in Fig. 2b. This approach can be used in LES (as we shall discuss in section 8), but it is impractical in the adiabatic parcel and DNS-like frameworks because the number of droplets in the subensemble decays with time as droplets disperse and leave the sampling volume.

A second approach for local sampling is by using reflecting boundary conditions on z and w at the bottom and top horizontal boundaries of the sampling volume. These boundaries are separated by a constant distance equal to Δ , thus enforcing $\tilde{\Delta} = \Delta$ as illustrated in Fig. 2b. This treatment was used by Abade and Albuquerque (2024) in an extended version of the eddy-hopping model operating in mixed-phase adiabatic parcels. Reflecting boundary conditions preserve the number of

FIG. 3. Scatterplots of $a' = a - \langle a \rangle$ and $z' = z - \langle z \rangle$ to illustrate the local sampling in an adiabatic parcel of size Δ enforced by using (a) reflecting boundary conditions (red dots) and (b) modified PBCs (blue dots). Gray dots in (a) and (b) are for an unbounded sampling volume (nonlocal sampling) of growing length $\tilde{\Delta}(t) \sim t^{1/2}$. The results consider the reversible condensation regime. (c) The time evolution ($\tau_\Delta = \varepsilon^{-1/3} \Delta^{2/3}$) of the filtered standard deviation $\sigma_a(\Delta)$ for fixed filter width Δ (reflecting top and bottom walls and modified PBC), while $\sigma_a[\tilde{\Delta}(t)]$ continuously grows along with the sampling length scale $\tilde{\Delta}(t)$ in the unbounded case. Simulations are for $N = 100 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\varepsilon = 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$, $\langle S \rangle = 0$, and $\langle a \rangle = a_0 = 100 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^2$.

representative droplets in the sampling volume. However, it can be used only in the adiabatic parcel framework under the reversible condensation regime. Reflecting boundary conditions are applied according to the algorithm of Wilson and Fleisch (1993), which is summarized in appendix A for clarity.

A third approach uses *modified* PBC in the vertical direction to be explained below. As (16) and Figs. 2, 3a, and 3b indicate, the sampling volume containing droplets is embedded in a cloud which has a mean squared radius gradient $\bar{\gamma}_a (\approx \partial_z a_{\text{rev}} = 2DA_1\tau_s)$ in the z direction. This resembles nonequilibrium (particle-based) molecular dynamics simulations of fluid under shear (Lees and Edwards 1972) with constant velocity gradient $\gamma_u = du/dz$ in the z direction.³ In this case, PBC must be used not only on particle positions but also on particle velocities (Lees and Edwards 1972).

In our turbulent condensation problem, modified PBC (in contrast to *usual* PBC) not only remaps droplet vertical positions but also adjusts the droplet radii as droplets cross the bottom and top horizontal boundaries of the sampling volume. Usual and modified PBC are contrasted in Fig. 4. Imagine that a droplet leaves the sampling volume at the top boundary (point P in Figs. 4a and 4b) with a large squared radius. Under *usual* periodic boundary conditions, the droplet will be reintroduced into the sampling volume at the bottom boundary (point P' of Fig. 4a) with its large squared radius unaltered. However, due to the gradient $\bar{\gamma}_a$, the squared

radius must be also adjusted when the droplet is reintroduced at point P' (as in Fig. 4b) to produce a stable squared radius gradient over sufficiently long periods in the steady state. The modified PBC scheme is described in detail in appendix B.

As for reflecting boundaries (Abade and Albuquerque 2024), modified PBC preserves the number of representative droplets in the ensemble. As an advantage, modified PBC can be presumably applied in DNS-like studies as well (at least in the droplet-tracer limit, where sedimentation and droplet inertia are neglected). Also, modified PBC can be used to extract the fine-grained DSD due to deviations from the reversible condensation regime, as we shall discuss in section 5.

Figure 3 shows that reflecting boundaries and the modified PBC are effective to enforce local sampling of the DSD and produce the same well-defined filtered variance $\sigma_a(\Delta)$ for filter width Δ .

c. A reduced stochastic model

It follows from previous sections that the eddy-hopping model builds up correlations between droplet sizes and droplet vertical positions. The resulting fine-grained DSDs are spatially inhomogeneous (along the vertical direction) and in general differ from the Δ -dependent filtered DSD. It is then instructive to consider a simple model of stochastic condensation [as the one discussed by Chandrakar et al. (2016) and Saito et al. (2019)] that coarsely represents DSD broadening in an idealized scenario, where the statistics of the droplet sizes is imagined to be spatially homogeneous. This scenario emerges in a certain type of DNS-like model of turbulent condensation that mimics an idealized homogeneous and unbounded cloud (to be discussed later in section 6).

³ In molecular dynamic simulations of fluid under shear, the sampling volume containing the particles is considered as being embedded in a fluid which has a constant velocity gradient $\gamma_u = du/dz$ in the z direction.

FIG. 4. (a) Under usual PBC, a large droplet leaves the sampling box at some point P and is reintroduced into the box at P' with its radius unaltered. Accordingly, a small droplet that leaves the box at Q is reintroduced at Q' with the same radius. (b) The modified PBC shrinks the radius of a large droplet as it is reintroduced at P' after leaving the box at the point P . Accordingly, modified PBC expands the radius of a small droplet as it is reintroduced at Q' after leaving the box at the point Q .

The reduced model comprises two equations, one for a and the other for S :

$$da = 2DS dt, \quad (20)$$

$$dS = -\frac{S}{\tau_s} dt + \sqrt{\frac{2\sigma_s^2}{\tau_s}} dW(t). \quad (21)$$

Unlike the eddy-hopping model, the reduced model describes only two jointly distributed stochastic variables a and S , regardless of the droplet positions and velocities. Also, the noise representing fluctuations enters directly in (20) for supersaturation. Here, we assume the model parameters σ_s and τ_s in (20) can be estimated. For the moment, we leave unspecified the physical processes that produce supersaturation fluctuations (and determine σ_s and τ_s).

It can be shown [see, e.g., Chandrakar et al. (2016)] that this reduced model produces the same asymptotic continuous growth [(18)] of the variance of a (for t sufficiently longer than τ_s):

$$\sigma_a^2 = Kt, \quad t \gg \tau_s, \quad (22)$$

where $K \equiv 8D^2\sigma_s^2\tau_s$. However, if fluctuations in S are created by sources other than vertical velocity fluctuations, then the continuous growth of σ_a^2 in (22) does not have the spatial interpretation as in (18) because a and S are decoupled from the droplet transport. The resulting fine-grained DSD is *spatially homogeneous* and thus coincides with the filtered DSD for arbitrary filter width Δ .

The underlying sources of supersaturation fluctuations in the reduced model (as those due to vertical velocity fluctuations are excluded) may be stationary external boundary conditions that sustain the scalar fluctuations against turbulent mixing and scalar dissipation.⁴ This external boundary condition determines the supersaturation variance σ_s^2 , a model parameter. The other model parameter is τ_s , the Lagrangian integral scale of S [(24)], which is difficult to measure in Lagrangian coordinates. Then, τ_s can be estimated by assuming the second-order Lagrangian structure function of S $\langle dS^2(\tau) \rangle \equiv \langle [S(t+\tau) - S(t)]^2 \rangle$ follows the Kolmogorov scaling:

$$\langle dS^2(\tau) \rangle = C_1\chi_s\tau, \quad (23)$$

where C_1 is a constant, χ_s is the mean dissipation rate of the scalar variance (S'^2), and the time lag τ lies in the inertial range (i.e., $\tau_\eta \ll \tau \ll \tau_s$, where τ_η is the Kolmogorov time scale). Relations of type (23) were thoroughly tested by Chandrakar et al. (2023) in high-resolution simulations of the Pi chamber setup.

⁴ In the Pi chamber, stationary conditions at the top, bottom, and sidewalls determine how scalar fluctuations are maintained against turbulent mixing and scalar dissipation. Also, as the characteristic vertical displacement of air parcels in the Pi chamber is a negligible fraction of the length scale $1/A_1$, different adiabatic cooling rates arising from turbulent fluctuations in the vertical velocities cannot be regarded as a source of variability in droplet growth conditions.

Then, squaring (21), taking the ensemble average, and using (23) yield the amplitude $\sqrt{C_1 \chi_s}$ ($= \sqrt{2\sigma_s^2/\tau_s}$) of the random term in (21) and the time scale $\tau_s = 2\sigma_s^2/(C_1 \chi_s)$. The model parameters (σ_s, τ_s) here have no correlation with the statistics of droplet vertical velocities.

The four-equation eddy-hopping model (section 4) and the two-equation reduced stochastic model described above serve as prototypes of the two classes of DNS-like models we shall discuss later in section 6.

d. *The incomplete equivalence between reduced and eddy-hopping models*

The scaling $\sigma_a^2 \sim t$ [(18) and (22)] for the variance is robust and will be observed in both eddy-hopping and reduced stochastic models. As $da/dt \propto S(t)$ (a linear relation) and $S(t)$ is a stochastic process, σ_a^2 will eventually grow like t for times sufficiently longer than the supersaturation autocorrelation time τ_s , defined as

$$\tau_s = \frac{1}{\sigma_s^2} \int_0^\infty R_s(t) dt, \tag{24}$$

where $R_s(t) = \langle S'(t_0)S'(t_0 + t) \rangle$ is the supersaturation autocorrelation function, with $S' = S - \langle S \rangle$ and $\sigma_s^2 = R_s(0)$.

However, the essential point here is the *source* of the random fluctuations of $S(t)$. The DSD broadening described by the reduced model [(20) and (21)] can be regarded as *strictly local* only if the noise in (21), which is parameterized by σ_s and τ_s , is due to sources other than vertical velocity fluctuations. If the parameterization of supersaturation fluctuations includes any source due to vertical velocity fluctuations, then this forcing will create correlations between droplet radii and droplet vertical positions. This implies that the fine-grained and filtered DSDs no longer coincide and the filtered DSD will depend on the filter width Δ .

It has been suggested (Saito et al. 2021) that the two-equation model above [(20) and (21)] can be obtained by simplifying the eddy-hopping model. Saito et al. (2021) showed that in the large-scale limit, where the microphysics is fast compared to the slow turbulent mixing in large systems ($\tau_{ph} \ll \tau_{mix} \sim \Delta^{2/3}$), the vertical velocity fluctuation w can be eliminated from the stochastic eddy-hopping model. As shown by Saito et al. (2021), the statistical properties of supersaturation fluctuations in the simplified model [viz., $\sigma_s, R_s(t)$, and thus τ_s] converge to those of the model without simplification as the ratio $\tau_{mix}/\tau_{ph} \gg 1$ increases (i.e., as one approaches the large scale limit).

However, the elimination of w from the description masks the issues of nonlocal sampling discussed in section 4b. Also, it removes the possibility of enforcing local sampling by using the approaches discussed in section 4b.

Moreover, although w is eliminated in the simplified model of Saito et al. (2021), vertical velocity fluctuations are the hidden source of supersaturation fluctuations as σ_w and τ_w remain in the expressions for the parameters σ_s and τ_s [see Eqs. (22) and (30) in Saito et al. (2021)]. At first sight, this procedure may suggest a “statistical equivalence” between the eddy-hopping model and its reduced version. However, this equivalence is incomplete, as the reduction procedure fixes

only σ_s and $R_s(t)$, and thus hides correlations between droplet sizes and droplet vertical positions.

In an LES setting with particle-based microphysics, a proper implementation of the eddy hopping as an SGS microphysical model requires coupling between the vertical SGS droplet transport and the vertical velocity fluctuation w that drives the SGS supersaturation fluctuations, as we shall discuss in section 8. Then, the vertical velocity fluctuation should remain as an explicit model variable.

5. **Deviations from the quasisteady supersaturation**

As discussed in section 3, deviations from any of the three main assumptions [from (i) to (iii)] underlying the reversible condensation scenario will work to destroy correlations between droplet size and droplet vertical position, creating conditions for strictly local broadening of the fine-grained DSD. The eddy-hopping model incorporates two of these assumptions, namely, that all droplets in the ensemble experience the same supersaturation relaxation time τ_s and that droplets follow the airflow as tracers (sedimentation and inertia are neglected). The eddy-hopping model then allows for deviations from the quasisteady supersaturation [(4)], being these deviations the only possible cause of the broadening of the fine-grained DSD in the adiabatic (nonentraining) parcel framework.

In general, the supersaturation driven by vertical velocity fluctuations is frequency dependent, that is, its response to fluctuations in the vertical velocity is retarded. This is clear after further inspection of (12) and (15), which gives the linear relation:

$$S(\omega) = \varphi(\omega)w(\omega), \quad \varphi(\omega) = \frac{A_1 \tau_s}{1 - i\omega \tau_s}, \tag{25}$$

between the Fourier–Laplace transforms $S(\omega)$ and $w(\omega)$ of $S(t)$ and $w(t)$, respectively, where ω is the frequency, and $\varphi(\omega) = \varphi'(\omega) + i\varphi''(\omega) = |\varphi|e^{i\theta}$ is the amplitude- and phase-modifying transfer function. The phase modification $\theta = \arctan(\varphi''/\varphi')$ is due to the generally nonzero imaginary part $\varphi''(\omega)$. More details are summarized in appendix C.

The quasisteady approximation corresponds to the low-frequency limit $\omega\tau_s \rightarrow 0$, where $S(\omega)$ and $w(\omega)$ [and thus $S_{qs}(\omega) \equiv A_1 \tau_s w(\omega)$] are in phase (as φ'' vanishes). For finite and high frequencies $\omega\tau_s$, $S(\omega)$ and $w(\omega)$ are phase shifted. Then, the close link between supersaturation and vertical velocity is broken (see, e.g., Khvorostyanov and Curry 1999) and the condensation is no longer perfectly reversible (even when there is no variability in τ_s among the droplets of the ensemble).

The quasisteady approximation [(4)] cannot represent high-frequency supersaturation fluctuations, that is, fluctuations occurring on time scales shorter than the time constant τ_s characterizing the relaxation of S to the quasisteady value S_{qs} [(15)]. Associated with τ_s , there is a spatial length scale ℓ_s (the supersaturation relaxation length). It can be estimated (Kabanov et al. 1971; Clark and Hall 1979) as follows:

$$\ell_s \sim e^{1/2} \tau_s^{3/2}, \tag{26}$$

FIG. 5. Fine-grained vs filtered DSD for finite τ_s . (a) Scatterplot of z' and a' (blue dots) along with the broad filtered DSD of filter width $\Delta = 50$ m (gray line) and the much narrower fine-grained DSD of *vanishing* filter width (red line); (b) time evolution of the filtered $\sigma_a(\Delta)$ and fine-grained $\sigma_a(0)$ standard deviation of a . Simulations using the eddy-hopping model with modified PBC are for $N = 100 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\varepsilon = 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$, $\Delta = 50$ m, $\langle S \rangle = 0$, and $\langle a \rangle = a_0 = 100 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^2$. The scale height is $H_a \approx 3$ m in the steady state.

where ε is the mean dissipation rate. The relation [(26)] is obtained on dimensional grounds by assuming that both τ_s and ℓ_s lie in Kolmogorov's inertial range of cloud turbulence. This allows us to express the range of description supported by the quasisteady approximation in terms of spatial length scales: The quasisteady supersaturation fluctuation S_{qs} cannot represent microphysical variability due to vertical velocities of eddies of spatial scales smaller than ℓ_s .

On short times compared to τ_s (or small length scales compared to ℓ_s), the link between S and w is weaker and the condensation reversibility is broken [see, e.g., Khvorostyanov and Curry (1999)]. This irreversibility allows w to generate supersaturation fluctuations S that may produce strictly local DSD broadening. These processes occurring on time scales $\leq \tau_s$ and length scales $\leq \ell_s$ are resolved (although coarsely represented) by the eddy-hopping model if (11)–(14) are numerically integrated using a short time step $\delta t \ll \tau_s$. This is shown in the scatterplots of z' and a' in Fig. 5a for finite τ_s and ℓ_s , where a fine-grained DSD (red line) of finite breadth [measured by $\sigma_a(0)$] can be observed. The fine-grained DSD in the steady state is, however, much narrower than the filtered DSD (gray line) for a filter width $\Delta = 50$ m, as shown in Fig. 5b.

Also, we may argue that inside a (generally small) volume of order $\sim \ell_s^3$, droplet sizes and droplet vertical positions are approximately uncorrelated. This feature has been noticed by

Clark and Hall (1979) in the region of the activation layer, where the relaxation time τ_s and its associated length scale ℓ_s are enlarged compared to the conditions in the cloud core. As one advances toward the cloud core, inhomogeneities on scales larger than ℓ_s dominate and the regime of (large scale) nearly reversible condensation is restored. Figure 6 shows the increase in the breadth $\sigma_a(0)$ of the fine-grained DSD with τ_s (and ℓ_s). The time constant τ_s and the corresponding length ℓ_s were changed by considering different droplet number concentrations N as indicated in Fig. 6. Thus, in a scenario where supersaturation fluctuations S (and the resulting variability in droplet growth conditions) arise from turbulent vertical velocity fluctuations only, effective local broadening of the fine-grained DSD can emerge.

Finally, we note that an alternative picture can be provided by examining the power spectrum $E_s(\omega)$ of the supersaturation fluctuation $S(t)$ driven by vertical velocity fluctuations $w(t)$. In appendix C, we derive the expression for $E_s(\omega)$ predicted by the eddy-hopping model.

Figure 7 shows the dimensionless spectrum $\hat{E}_s(\hat{\omega})$ [(C3)] as a function of the dimensionless frequency $\hat{\omega} = \omega \tau_s$ for different values of $\alpha = \tau_s / \tau_w$, the ratio of the integral time scales of $S(t)$ and $w(t)$. As $\tau_s = 1 / (\tau_{\text{ph}}^{-1} + \tau_{\text{mix}}^{-1}) \approx \min\{\tau_{\text{ph}}, \tau_{\text{mix}}\}$ and $\tau_{\text{mix}} \approx \tau_w$, the parameter α is closely related to the inverse of the Damköhler number Da , defined as $\text{Da} \equiv \tau_{\text{mix}} / \tau_{\text{ph}}$. It is clear from Fig. 7 that the major contribution to the variance

FIG. 6. Fine-grained $\sigma_a(0)$ for different droplet number concentrations N (the corresponding τ_s and ℓ_s in the steady state are also indicated). Larger τ_s (and ℓ_s) leads to broader fine-grained DSD. Simulation parameters are the same as in Fig. 5, except for N .

$$\sigma_s^2(\Delta) = \int_{\omega_\Delta}^{\infty} E_s(\omega) d\omega, \quad \omega_\Delta \sim \varepsilon^{1/3} \Delta^{-2/3}, \quad (27)$$

and hence to the filtered variance $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$ of droplet squared radius, comes from the lower frequency range. As the ratio $\alpha = \tau_s/\tau_w$ increases (Da decreases), this frequency range shifts toward larger frequencies.

Practically, the high-frequency limit in (27) is the maximum resolved frequency, which is specified by the time step δt used to numerically integrate the stochastic eddy-hopping model [(11)]–[(14)]. Physically, the high-frequency limit in the eddy-hopping model should be understood as

$$\tau_s^{-1} \ll \omega \ll \tau_\eta^{-1}, \quad (28)$$

where τ_η is the Kolmogorov time scale. The upper bound τ_η^{-1} follows from the requirement [see, e.g., Rodean (1996)] that the time increment dt in (13) lies in the inertial subrange (i.e., $dt \gg \tau_\eta$). Also, we note that the high-frequency limit [(28)] is subtle in the regime of fast microphysics (short τ_{ph} and small ε), as the time scales τ_s and τ_η may not be sufficiently well separated.

In the so-called DNS-like models of type A (to be discussed in section 6), the high-frequency limit [(27)] is specified by the spatial resolution δx of the computational grid. To resolve the high-frequency limit $\omega \gg \tau_s^{-1}$, the spatial resolution $\delta x \ll \ell_s$ in DNS-like studies should be fine enough relative to the length scale ℓ_s associated with τ_s (Clark and Hall 1979).

Finally, we note that for high frequencies, the effects of sedimentation (in decreasing the interaction between droplets and small turbulent eddies) may become significant, as we shall discuss in section 7.

FIG. 7. Dimensionless power spectrum $\hat{E}_s(\hat{\omega})$ of supersaturation fluctuations as a function of the dimensionless frequency $\hat{\omega} = \omega\tau_s$ for different values of the parameter $\alpha = \tau_s/\tau_w$. The arrow to the left indicates the direction of increasing Damköhler number $Da \equiv \tau_{mix}/\tau_{ph}$.

6. DNS-like studies

DNS studies⁵ of turbulent condensation may be separated into two types based on how supersaturation fluctuations are created:

Type A by local vertical velocity fluctuations via the adiabatic cooling effect or

Type B by random forcing of the thermodynamic scalars (temperature T and vapor mixing ratio q , or supersaturation S) applied isotropically on the large scales of the computational box of size Δ .

Appendix D summarizes the equations comprising the DNS models of types A and B. The stochastic eddy-hopping and reduced models described in section 4 serve, respectively, as useful prototypes of DNS models of types A and B.

a. DNS-like models of type B

DNS studies of type B neglect the adiabatic cooling effect and simulate supersaturation fluctuations solely produced by the scalar forcing at large scales $\sim \Delta$. This scalar forcing mimics the effects of external boundary conditions that sustain scalar fluctuations against turbulent mixing. The works by Paoli and Shariff (2009), Siewert et al. (2017), and Saito et al. (2019) belong to this type of DNS study, which actually models turbulent condensation in an unbounded and homogeneous cloud. General features of DNS models of type B can be understood by analyzing the reduced stochastic model

⁵ Here and henceforth, DNS actually means “DNS-like” studies as they also include the so-called scaled-up DNS of Thomas et al. (2020) and implicit ILES studies of Grabowski and Thomas (2021) and Grabowski et al. (2022b,a).

discussed in section 4c, provided σ_s^2 is due to sources other than vertical velocity fluctuations.

DNS models of type B produce polydisperse droplet dispersions with spatially homogeneous droplet size statistics as does the reduced stochastic model of section 4c. In this scenario, usual PBCs in all directions are applicable to mimic an unbounded system, where cloud boundaries are imagined to be removed to infinity. The fine-grained DSDs coincide with filtered DSDs (for arbitrary filter width), and these models are thus free from artifacts that could mask the real origin of the observed local DSD broadening. This is not the case of DNS model of type A, as we shall discuss below.

b. DNS-like models of type A

DNS studies of type A do not apply any large-scale scalar forcing but rely on the local adiabatic cooling effect (driven by vertical velocity fluctuations) as the only source of supersaturation variability. Their purpose is to confine the problem of turbulent condensation to a study of the effect of local or “internal” sources of thermodynamic variability caused by velocity fluctuations on a range of length scales smaller or on the order of Δ . The works by Vaillancourt et al. (2002), Celani et al. (2005, 2008, 2009), Lanotte et al. (2009), Sardina et al. (2015, 2018), Saito and Gotoh (2018), Thomas et al. (2020), Grabowski and Thomas (2021), and Grabowski et al. (2022b,a) belong to this rather problematic class of DNS models.

DNS models of type A give rise to polydisperse droplet dispersions with droplet size statistics that is spatially inhomogeneous in the vertical direction as in the stochastic eddy-hopping model. In this case, the periodic computational box containing the droplets should be regarded as a small sample embedded in a cloud which has a mean squared radius gradient in the vertical direction (section 4b). Despite being ill suited for this scenario, the usual PBC (Fig. 4a) in the vertical direction has been the rule in DNS models of type A, thus causing numerical artifacts.

Issues with DNS studies of this type were generally suggested by Prabhakaran et al. (2022). Their argument was formulated in terms of “inadequate representation of vertical turbulent transport” and on the fact that “all the cloud droplets have the same life time” in these idealized frameworks. Here, we refine the statements of Prabhakaran et al. (2022) and explain in more detail the sources of the numerical artifacts in DNS models of type A.

c. Artifacts in DNS models of type A

The problem with DNS studies of type A arises from misuse of PBC in the direction (vertical) along which the statistics of droplet sizes is spatially inhomogeneous. Usual PBC (illustrated in Fig. 4a) takes a cloud droplet that had left the computational box, say, through the top, and puts it back at the bottom of the domain (keeping the droplet size). If these droplet trajectories (corrected by usual PBC) were “unfolded,” then it would reveal that droplets actually diffuse in the vertical due to turbulent fluctuations. Thus, the actual averaging length scale $\tilde{\Delta}$ grows beyond the computational box size Δ (where momentum forcing is applied) and follows the scaling

$\sim t^{1/2}$ as in the eddy-hopping model operating in adiabatic parcels (see section 4) and illustrated in Fig. 2a.⁶

Alternatively, the issue can be understood in the reversible condensation scenario, which emerges on the large scales ($\gg \ell_s$) inside the DNS computational box. We argue that the usual PBC, which returns a large droplet (that had left the computational box at the top) back to the bottom of the domain (and keeps its large radius), artificially breaks the large-scale near reversibility of the condensation. It enforces that large and small droplets coexist in the computational box of characteristic size Δ and incorrectly predict DSD continuous broadening, which cannot be regarded as local. This is shown in Fig. 8. The gray dots in Fig. 8a show that the usual PBC decorrelates a and z by vertically mixing small and large droplets in the computational box. The corresponding breadth $\sigma_a[\tilde{\Delta}(t)]$ grows continuously in time (Fig. 8b). Conversely, modified PBC preserves the vertical gradient of the droplet squared radius (blue dots in Fig. 8a). The breadths $\sigma_a(\Delta)$ and $\sigma_a(0)$ of the corresponding filtered and fine-grained DSDs reach quasistationary values with $\sigma_a(\Delta) > \sigma_a(0)$ (Fig. 8).

Also, the usual PBC in DNS models of type A vertically mixes large and small droplets and creates spurious spatial correlations between droplets of different sizes at short separations. This may artificially enhance droplet collision probabilities, which is essential for the onset of collision-coalescence. We shall discuss this further in section 8c. For instance, the observation in DNS data by Celani et al. (2005) that small and large droplets cohabit in small volumes (and that it may enhance droplet collision probabilities) might have been distorted by the artificial effects of usual PBC.

We note that besides using modified PBC, one needs to use sufficiently high grid resolutions to properly predict fine-grained DSDs and the spatial correlations between “large” and “small” droplets. The analysis of Clark and Hall (1979) and our discussion in section 5 suggest that actual local DSD broadening can be observed only on small length scales compared to the supersaturation relaxation length scale ℓ_s . Then, the DNS grid needs to resolve small scales $\leq \ell_s$, as anticipated by Clark and Hall (1979). The local broadening arising from the irreversible coupling between supersaturation fluctuations and the vertical motion of air parcels is expected to be enhanced around the activation layer (larger τ_s and ℓ_s) and suppressed under cloud core conditions (smaller τ_s and ℓ_s) as indicated in Fig. 6.

The issues discussed above are more pronounced in scaled-up DNS (Thomas et al. 2020) and implicit LES (ILES) studies (Grabowski and Thomas 2021; Grabowski et al. 2022b,a), where sedimentation is neglected and the system size Δ (ranging from several meters to several tens of meters) is sufficiently larger than ℓ_s . On the other hand, the artifacts due to

⁶ Note that models producing local fluctuations in T (or S) by fluctuations in w via the adiabatic cooling effect implicitly assume that air parcels ascending in the computational box expand due to the vertical decrease in the base-state hydrostatic pressure. This vertical gradient in the base-state pressure evidently breaks the translational invariance within the DNS computational box. This inhomogeneity is absent in DNS studies of type B.

FIG. 8. (a) Scatterplot of a' and z' at $t/\tau_\Delta = 2$ using usual PBC (gray dots) and modified PBC (blue dots) for a background average supersaturation $\langle S \rangle = 0.01$. Usual PBC artificially decorrelates a' and z' by mixing small and large droplets in the computational box. (b) Time evolution of the standard deviations $\sigma_a[\tilde{\Delta}(t)]$ (usual PBC), $\sigma_a(\Delta)$, and $\sigma_a(0)$ (corresponding to the filtered and fine-grained DSDs obtained under modified PBC). The results were obtained by numerical integration of the eddy-hopping model equations (a prototype for DNS-like models of type A). For $\langle S \rangle > 0$, the droplets grow on average, and then, both $\bar{v}_a \sim 1/\langle r \rangle_\Delta$ and the ratio H_a/Δ decrease with time. The scale height [(10)] is $H_a \approx 7$ m at $t/\tau_\Delta = 5$ and reaches $H_a \approx 18$ m in the quasisteady state. The difference between the filtered $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$ and fine-grained $\sigma_a^2(0)$ variances decreases with time.

usual PBC are not easily noticed in high-resolution DNS studies of small systems, such as in Vaillancourt et al. (2002), where Δ is only about 10 cm due to limited computational resources.

The analysis of such small systems is subtle. First, as Δ may not be sufficiently larger than ℓ_s (τ_Δ not sufficiently larger than τ_s), the scales where reversible and irreversible condensation occurs may not be well separated within the system. Second, Δ may not be sufficiently larger than H_a , making the correlations between droplet sizes and droplet vertical position less evident. Third, DNS studies of *small* systems only represent the supersaturation fluctuations driven by velocity fluctuations due to correspondingly *small* turbulent eddies. As we shall discuss in the next section, droplet sedimentation becomes important in mitigating supersaturation fluctuations due to small eddies. Also, the supersaturation sedimenting droplet experience is usually less correlated than the Lagrangian fluid supersaturation, being this decorrelating effect of sedimentation relatively more important at small scales.

7. Sedimentation and droplet inertia

Here, we examine more closely the neglect of sedimentation and droplet inertia effects. Our treatment assumed the

droplets follow the turbulent airflow $\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, being the droplet trajectory \mathbf{X} calculated via $\dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{U}[\mathbf{X}(t), t]$. In this *droplet-tracer limit*, the microphysics is tightly coupled with the droplet transport and the positive correlation between droplet sizes and their vertical positions is maximized.

Sedimentation and droplet inertia lead to the relative motion of the droplets and the surrounding fluid. As the droplets may drift from one fluid element to another, the supersaturation droplet experience is usually less correlated than the Lagrangian fluid supersaturation. Thus, droplet inertia and sedimentation work to weaken the correlation between microphysics and droplet transport in the scenario of w -driven microphysical variability.

More generally, the droplet location $\mathbf{X}(t)$ and velocity $\mathbf{V}(t)$ are described by

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}} = \mathbf{V}, \quad \dot{\mathbf{V}} = (\mathbf{U} - \mathbf{V})/\tau_d + \mathbf{g}, \quad (29)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \equiv \mathbf{U}[\mathbf{X}(t), t]$, $\tau_d = 2\rho_w r^2/(9\mu)$ is the droplet response time, ρ_w is the density of liquid water, μ is the viscosity of the surrounding air, and $\mathbf{g} = g\hat{\mathbf{e}}_g$ is the gravity acceleration. Let u_λ and $\tau_\lambda = \lambda/u_\lambda$ denote the characteristic velocity and time scales of turbulent eddies of size λ . We then scale the velocities \mathbf{V}

and \mathbf{U} with u_λ , time with τ_λ , and assume τ_d sufficiently smaller than τ_λ to write the approximate solution to (29) for \mathbf{V} in terms of dimensionless variables:

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{U} + \text{Sv}_\lambda \hat{\mathbf{e}}_g - \text{St}_\lambda \dot{\mathbf{U}} + O(\text{St}_\lambda^2), \quad (30)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{U}} = \partial_t \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{U}$ is the total derivative of \mathbf{U} (the same symbols were used for dimensional and dimensionless variables).

Equation (30) implies that the relative degree at which droplets will lag the airflow on a length scale λ is controlled by two (λ -dependent) dimensionless parameters: the Stokes number $\text{St}_\lambda \equiv \tau_d/\tau_\lambda$ and the settling number $\text{Sv}_\lambda \equiv \tau_{dg}/u_\lambda$, where $\tau_{dg} = w_{\text{sed}}$ is the droplet terminal sedimentation velocity. The droplet-tracer limit considered in this work corresponds to $\tau_d \rightarrow 0$ and vanishing Stokes and settling numbers.

The assessment of sedimentation and droplet inertia effects (through the scale-dependent parameters St_λ and Sv_λ) should be consistent with the range of length scales represented by the turbulent condensation model (stochastic eddy hopping or DNS). Because the stochastic eddy-hopping model was derived to describe motions in the inertial range, we should examine St_λ and Sv_λ for λ in this very same range, where $u_\lambda = (\epsilon\lambda)^{1/3}$ and $\tau_\lambda = \epsilon^{-1/3}\lambda^{2/3}$. The relevant length scales are then Δ and the supersaturation relaxation length scale ℓ_s . Typically, for the relatively small droplet sizes ($\langle r \rangle = 10 \mu\text{m}$) considered in Fig. 5, the maximum values of the Stokes and settling parameters ($\text{St}_\Delta \approx 10^{-5}$, $\text{Sv}_\Delta \approx 0.03$, $\text{St}_{\ell_s} \approx 4 \times 10^{-4}$, and $\text{Sv}_{\ell_s} \approx 0.2$) indicate that the effects of inertia and sedimentation may be neglected to a reasonable approximation.

For high-resolution DNS studies (e.g., Vaillancourt et al. 2002), we can examine St_η and Sv_η at scales λ near the Kolmogorov length scale η . For the parameters considered in Fig. 5, the values $\text{St}_\eta \approx 0.01$ and $\text{Sv}_\eta \approx 1.2$ indicate that sedimentation effects are nonnegligible as reported by Vaillancourt et al. (2002). However, this is a regime in which the (small-scale, short-time) processes that come into play are not describable by the stochastic eddy-hopping model.

Finally, the effect that the supersaturation experienced by sedimenting droplets is less correlated than the Lagrangian fluid supersaturation can be roughly parameterized in (12) by using an *effective* mixing time scale $\tau_{\text{mix}}^{\text{eff}}$. This may combine the usual mixing time scale τ_{mix} with the sedimentation time scale $\tau_{\text{sed},\Delta}$, as suggested by Tölle and Krueger (2014):

$$\tau_{\text{mix}}^{\text{eff}} = \left(\frac{1}{\tau_{\text{mix}}} + \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{sed}}} \right)^{-1} \approx \tau_{\text{mix}} \frac{1}{1 + \text{Sv}_\Delta}, \quad (31)$$

where $\tau_{\text{sed},\Delta}$ is the time it takes a droplet to fall through an eddy of size Δ . The approximated expression in the right-most side of (31) assumes $\tau_{\text{mix}} \approx \tau_\Delta$ with Δ -dependent settling number Sv_Δ written in terms of the ratio of the two time scales involved, and $\text{Sv}_\Delta = \tau_\Delta/\tau_{\text{sed},\Delta}$. However, for the relatively small droplet sizes considered here and for Δ in the inertial range, the settling number $\text{Sv}_\Delta \sim 0.01$ is sufficiently small to safely assume $\tau_{\text{mix}}^{\text{eff}} \approx \tau_{\text{mix}}$.

An extended version of the eddy-hopping model that accounts for the effects of sedimentation and droplet inertia

(and thus can be applied to larger droplet sizes) remains to be formulated.

8. Eddy-hopping model as a subgrid scheme in LES

If used as an SGS condensation scheme in LES with particle-based microphysics, the eddy-hopping model will predict filtered DSD that tend to be broader than those proposed under the uniform condensation approximation, where all droplets in a particular grid box experience the same filtered (grid-averaged) supersaturation $\langle S \rangle$. This has some implications that we shall discuss here.

First, to prevent the eddy-hopping model from predicting artificial DSD broadening (through the nonlocal sampling discussed for the adiabatic cloud parcel), the SGS turbulent transport of cloud droplets must be treated properly. Second, if the SGS scheme predicts a broader-filtered DSD, then this will certainly have an impact on the filtered condensation rate and hence on the filtered buoyancy production. Finally, broader-filtered DSDs may (at least in principle) indicate enhanced probabilities of collision-coalescence of droplets due to differential sedimentation. However, enhancement of collision probabilities actually occurs only if the physics underlying the SGS scheme is able to produce strictly local DSD broadening, which manifests itself mainly in the fine-grained DSD and not only in the filtered DSD.

a. SGS droplet transport

If the eddy-hopping model is used as a subgrid scheme in LES, then it must provide microphysical properties that refer to a particular grid box of size Δ , and hence, these properties must be sampled over a local averaging volume of characteristic size Δ . (Here, we assume for simplicity that the computational grid is isotropic with the same spatial resolution Δ in all directions.) To enforce this *local sampling* in LES, the SGS vertical transport of droplets must be driven by the same SGS velocity fluctuations w driving SGS supersaturation fluctuations S .

Otherwise, if the SGS model for condensation (including fluctuations in S driven by w) is decoupled from the SGS droplet transport, then it will spuriously overestimate the local width of the filtered DSD. For example, this is the risk we run while implementing in LES an SGS scheme like the simplified stochastic model suggested by Saito et al. (2021) (see section 4d), where the SGS vertical velocity fluctuation w no longer appears as a resolved model variable (although its underlying effects are parameterized in the simplified model).

Even when the droplet SGS transport is properly treated, the local variance of the filtered DSD may depend on the grid resolution Δ (the filter width) if it is larger or on the same order of H_a [(10)].

In an LES setting, w is the vertical component of the unresolved fluid velocity \mathbf{u} , and $w = \hat{\mathbf{e}}_z \cdot \mathbf{u}$. The velocity fluctuation \mathbf{u} can be modeled by a stochastic differential equation of the form (see, e.g., Pope 1994):

$$d\mathbf{u} = \boldsymbol{\alpha} dt - \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\tau_u} dt + \sqrt{\frac{2\sigma_u^2}{\tau_u}} d\mathbf{W}(t), \quad (32)$$

where $d\mathbf{W}(t)$ is the increment of an isotropic vector-valued Wiener process. Equation (32) applies to the general case of inhomogeneous turbulent flow in cloud-scale simulations. It differs from (13), which is for idealized adiabatic parcels filled with homogeneous turbulence, by the drift term (see, e.g., MacInnes and Bracco 1992):

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \nabla \cdot \langle \mathbf{u}\mathbf{u} \rangle_{\Delta} - \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \langle \mathbf{U} \rangle_{\Delta}, \quad (33)$$

where $\langle \mathbf{U} \rangle_{\Delta}$ is the filtered velocity field resolved by the dynamical core of the cloud LES scheme and $\langle \mathbf{u}\mathbf{u} \rangle_{\Delta}$ is the kinematic Reynolds stress tensor. [Here, the spatial filtering operation denoted by $\langle \cdot \cdot \rangle_{\Delta}$ is the same as defined in (2) for the DSD and considers the filter width equal to the LES resolution length Δ]. We note that (33) is essentially *kinematic*; that is, it arises as a kinematic step while writing the equation of motion for the fluctuation u from the Navier–Stokes (NS) equations for the full velocity $\mathbf{U} = \langle \mathbf{U} \rangle_{\Delta} + \mathbf{u}$. Also, τ_w in (13) for stationary homogeneous turbulence is an integral time scale, while τ_u in (32) for inhomogeneous turbulence represents a local velocity decorrelation time scale (see, e.g., Rodean 1996; Pope 2011). In the droplet-tracer regime, the droplet position \mathbf{X} is determined by integrating the stochastic differential equation (SDE) $d\mathbf{X} = [\langle \mathbf{U} \rangle_{\Delta} + \mathbf{u}]dt$. Equations (32) and (33) constitute the simplified Langevin model (SLM) for the fluid particle velocity fluctuation used in several applications (see, e.g., Pope 1994; MacInnes and Bracco 1992).

A scheme that couples w driving supersaturation fluctuations and vertical SGS droplet transport was recently implemented in cloud-scale simulations by Chandrakar et al. (2021). They use an expression derived by Weil et al. (2004) for the drift term $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, which is an approximation to (33). Also, Chandrakar et al. (2021) included an additional random forcing to the stochastic equation for the SGS Lagrangian supersaturation fluctuation, parameterized by a prescribed supersaturation standard deviation σ_s . Although Chandrakar et al. (2021) argue that this additional forcing arises from sources other than vertical velocity fluctuations, they specify σ_s in terms of the velocity fluctuation parameters σ_u and τ_u . A more physically appealing route to parameterize this stochastic forcing term of supersaturation fluctuations has been considered in Chandrakar et al. (2023) as we discussed in section 4c.

Finally, we briefly remark on the Lagrangian cloud model L3 by Hoffmann et al. (2019) and Hoffmann and Feingold (2019). In this model, the SGS droplet transport is not linked to the SGS vertical velocity fluctuations that partially contribute to the subgrid microphysical variability (through differential adiabatic cooling rates experienced by the cloud droplets). The L3 model combines an LES dynamical core with particle-based microphysics, where the so-called linear eddy model (LEM) [see, e.g., Kerstein (1988); Krueger et al. (1997)] is used to represent SGS turbulent mixing of the thermodynamic scalars. LEM solves the molecular diffusion of scalars on a one-dimensional grid (the LEM grid), which is periodically rearranged and compressed (using the so-called triple map) to simulate turbulent advection. As stated by Hoffmann et al. (2019) and Hoffmann and Feingold (2019), LEM also accounts for the variability of adiabatic cooling rates experienced by

different droplets in a given LES grid box. This arises from stochastic vertical motions due to the LEM triplet map, because the droplets experience the same rearrangements as the boxes of the LEM grid, which is aligned vertically. However, the actual SGS vertical droplet transport (which is due to stochastic velocities computed from the SGS turbulent kinetic energy k) and the stochastic vertical motions of the LEM grid boxes (due to the LEM triplet map) are apparently uncorrelated.

b. Grid-averaged condensation rate

In an LES setting of spatial resolution Δ , the balance equation for the filtered vapor mixing ratio $\langle q \rangle_{\Delta}$ has the form

$$\partial_t \langle q \rangle_{\Delta} = -\langle C \rangle_{\Delta} + \dots, \quad (34)$$

where $\langle C \rangle_{\Delta}$ is the spatially filtered (or grid-averaged) condensation rate. [Again, the spatial filtering $\langle \cdot \cdot \rangle_{\Delta}$ is the same as in (2) for the DSD.] The dots on the rhs of (34) denote other contributions to local changes in $\langle q \rangle_{\Delta}$, such as advection by the turbulent flow and molecular diffusion of water vapor.

In particle-based schemes (see, e.g., Shima et al. 2009; Arabas et al. 2015; Dziekan et al. 2019; Hoffmann et al. 2019), the filtered condensation rate is calculated directly. If we neglect for simplicity surface tension and solute effects and assume each droplet grows according to (3), then $\langle C \rangle_{\Delta}$ may be approximated as

$$\langle C \rangle_{\Delta} \approx \beta \sum_k r_k S_k, \quad \beta = \frac{4\pi\rho_w D}{\rho_d V_{\Delta}}, \quad (35)$$

where the sum is over all cloud droplets in the grid box of volume V_{Δ} , r_k is the radius of the k th droplet experiencing a supersaturation S_k ; and ρ_w and ρ_d are the densities of water and dry air, respectively. Also, we assume that the effective vapor diffusion coefficient D varies weakly in V_{Δ} .

By decomposing

$$r_k = \langle r \rangle_{\Delta} + r'_k, \quad S_k = \langle S \rangle_{\Delta} + S'_k, \quad (36)$$

where $\langle \cdot \cdot \rangle_{\Delta}$ here denotes averages over all droplets in V_{Δ} at a particular time, we may write

$$\langle C \rangle_{\Delta} = \beta N [\langle r \rangle_{\Delta} \langle S \rangle_{\Delta} + \langle r' S' \rangle_{\Delta}], \quad (37)$$

where N is the total droplet concentration in the grid box. Thus, the condensation rate $\approx \beta N \langle r \rangle_{\Delta} \langle S \rangle_{\Delta}$ under the uniform condensation approximation is increased by a factor proportional to the covariance $\langle r' S' \rangle_{\Delta} > 0$. For collisionless and non-sedimenting droplets, a positive correlation between S and r simply indicates that the large droplet tail of the filtered DSD is formed by those droplets that experienced higher supersaturation along their growth histories.

An equation like (37) was considered by Paoli and Sharif (2009). They stated that the *closure problem* of determining the filtered condensation term $\langle C \rangle_{\Delta}$ boils down to modeling the covariance $\langle r' S' \rangle_{\Delta}$ (i.e., writing it in terms of model resolved variables). The eddy-hopping model used as a particle-based SGS scheme provides a “closure” by explicitly calculating $\langle C \rangle_{\Delta}$

beyond the uniform condensation approximation. The resulting broadening of the filtered DSD predicted by the eddy-hopping model renders $\langle r'S \rangle_{\Delta} > 0$ and leads to increased local condensation rates compared with those obtained under uniform condensation. Enhanced filtered condensation rates do not require locally broader fine-grained DSDs; broader-filtered DSDs suffice.⁷ In contrast, enhanced droplet collision probabilities are supported by broader fine-grained DSDs only, as we shall discuss next.

c. Stochastic droplet coalescence

We were primarily focused so far on the DSD formed by the growth of collisionless droplets through condensation. However, the resulting DSD impacts the onset of gravity-induced droplet collision-coalescence.

Particle-based schemes for cloud microphysics, such as the superdroplet method (SDM) developed by Shima et al. (2009), treat droplet collision-coalescence in a probabilistic manner through a Monte Carlo method. This requires the probability P_{ij} that two droplets (labeled i and j) will coalesce inside a volume V during the time interval $(t, t + \delta t)$. This probability is given by

$$P_{ij} = K_{ij} \delta t / V, \quad (38)$$

where K_{ij} is the coalescence kernel. For droplet collisions induced by gravity through differential sedimentation,

$$K_{ij} \propto (r_i + r_j)^2 |w_{\text{sed}}(r_i) - w_{\text{sed}}(r_j)|, \quad (39)$$

where $w_{\text{sed}}(r)$ is a parameterization for the sedimentation velocity of a droplet of radius r .

An essential assumption underlying [(39)] is that the colliding droplets are well mixed inside V (see, e.g., Gillespie 1972; Shima et al. 2009; Dzikian and Pawlowska 2017) as spatial correlations between droplets⁸ are not parameterized in the collision kernel [(39)]. In an LES setting, it is generally assumed that the volume V in (38) is associated with the model spatial resolution, hence with the volume V_{Δ} of the computational grid box. Compared with the uniform condensation approximation, the eddy-hopping model used as an SGS condensation scheme tends to predict relatively broad-filtered DSD (of underlying sampling volume $\sim V_{\Delta}$). However, large

and small droplets forming the left and right tails of the predicted filtered DSD might not be well mixed in the volume V_{Δ} of the grid box. This is illustrated by scatterplots of a and z in Fig. 9. In fact, at the early stages of condensation, large and small droplets may be well separated in the computational grid box (as sedimentation is still too slow to effectively mix large and small droplets). This may lead to conceptual difficulties in calculating collision probabilities according to (39).

As discussed in section 5, the eddy-hopping model (relying on S driven solely by w) presumably produces droplet size statistics that are spatially homogeneous only on scales smaller or on the order of the supersaturation relaxation length scale ℓ_s (sedimentation and droplet inertia neglected). Then, one may argue that the well-mixed volume V has a characteristic linear size $V^{1/3} \leq \ell_s$, which may be much smaller (e.g., under cloud core conditions) than the volume V_{Δ} of the computational grid boxes. Also, $\langle n(r) \rangle_{\ell_s}$ (the filtered DSD with filter width $\sim \ell_s$) is much narrower than $\langle n(r) \rangle_{\Delta}$ (the filtered DSD with filter width $\sim \Delta$). Thus, droplet collision probabilities in $V \sim \ell_s^3$ may not be significantly enhanced (at least in the cloud core) under the turbulent condensation represented by the eddy-hopping model. Figure 9b shows how the dispersion $\sigma_{z|a}$ around the expected height $\langle z|a \rangle$ of a droplet of squared radius a depends on ℓ_s . As ℓ_s increases, the heights of a small droplet and a large droplet are more broadly distributed, thus enhancing the probability of finding droplets of different sizes close to each other.

9. Discussion

In this paper, we discussed that any turbulent condensation model that (in some degree) relates supersaturation fluctuations S experienced by cloud droplets with their vertical velocity fluctuations w will produce correlations between droplet sizes and droplet vertical positions in a cloudy volume. As a consequence, the statistics of droplet sizes produced by such a model will be spatially inhomogeneous along the vertical direction. This implies that the DSD will depend on the spatial scale over which the distribution is sampled. To systematically discuss this dependence on the sampling spatial scale, we have defined (section 2) the fine-grained DSD $n(r)$ and the filtered DSD $\langle n(r) \rangle_{\Delta}$ of filter width Δ . Thus, when the droplet size statistics is spatially inhomogeneous, then fine-grained DSDs that are locally narrow may render filtered DSDs that are locally broad in a discretized domain of spatial resolution Δ [provided Δ is sufficiently large than H_a defined in (10)].

A simple model that links S with w is the stochastic eddy-hopping model (Sardina et al. 2015; Grabowski and Abade 2017; Abade et al. 2018), where vertical velocity fluctuations cause supersaturation variability through the adiabatic cooling effect. The idea behind the eddy-hopping model is that, in a relatively large cloudy volume (say, of the size of a typical LES grid box), various cloud droplets (that are representative of the whole droplet population in this large cloudy volume) may experience different adiabatic cooling rates (hence different growth rates) depending on the vertical turbulent velocity of the air carrying these droplets.

⁷ Broader-filtered DSD may also impact grid-averaged optical properties as remarked by Jeffery et al. (2007) that “stochastic condensation provides a mechanism for decreasing grid-averaged cloud shortwave reflectivity while keeping cloud amount unchanged.”

⁸ Suppose that a “small” droplet of radius, say, $r_i = \langle r \rangle_{\Delta} - 2\sigma_r(\Delta)$ and a “large” one of radius $r_j = \langle r \rangle_{\Delta} + 2\sigma_r(\Delta)$ are located at the same grid box of size Δ , where the average radius $\langle r \rangle_{\Delta}$ and the standard deviation $\sigma_r(\Delta)$ refer to the filtered DSD $\langle n(r) \rangle_{\Delta}$. Now, let N_j denote the number concentration of large droplets. We define the radial distribution function $g_{ij}(\mathbf{x})$ for small and large droplets such that $N_j g_{ij}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}$ is the (ensemble) average number of large droplets in a volume element $d\mathbf{x}$ at the position \mathbf{x} from a small droplet. Under the well-mixed hypothesis, the gravity collision kernel [(39)] for the pair ij assumes $g_{ij}(R\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = 1$, where $R = r_i + r_j$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{x}/|\mathbf{x}|$, while in fact, $g_{ij}(R\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ should vanish when droplet radius is correlated with vertical position.

FIG. 9. (a) Scatterplot of a and z showing the conditional expected heights $\langle z|a_s \rangle$ and $\langle z|a_l \rangle$, respectively, of a small droplet (of squared radius a_s) and a large droplet (a_l). Considering the indicated conditional dispersion $\sigma_{z|a}$ in heights, these large and small droplets are in fact well separated (and *not* thoroughly mixed) in the volume of characteristic length Δ . (b) Conditional standard deviation $\sigma_{z|a}$ of heights (for a given a) as a function of the supersaturation length scale $\ell_s \sim \varepsilon^{1/2} \tau_s^{3/2}$. The points are for ε in the range $0.001\text{--}0.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$ and droplet number concentration N in the range $50\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Used as a stand-alone representation of turbulent condensation in an adiabatic parcel framework, the original version of the eddy-hopping model produces spurious broadening of the parcel DSD, where the standard deviation of droplet squared radius continuously grows in time. We have shown that this does not reflect an actual *local* DSD broadening [as supposed by Sardina et al. (2015), Grabowski and Abade (2017), Abade et al. (2018)], but arises from the implicit *non-local* sampling caused by the growth with time (like $\sim t^{1/2}$) of the spatial scale (or filter width) associated with the sampling volume containing the whole droplet population of the parcel. The sampling volume is implicitly related to the spatial extent of the droplet turbulent diffusion in the vertical direction, which is driven by the same vertical velocity fluctuations that cause variability in the supersaturation experienced by different droplets. To enforce local sampling in the adiabatic parcel framework, we considered (section 4b) alternative boundary conditions (reflecting and modified PBC) at the top and bottom horizontal boundaries of the sampling volume.

A certain type of DNS-like model of turbulent condensation (e.g., Vaillancourt et al. 2002; Celani et al. 2005, 2008, 2009; Lanotte et al. 2009; Sardina et al. 2015, 2018; Saito and Gotoh 2018; Thomas et al. 2020; Grabowski and Thomas 2021; Grabowski et al. 2022b,a), as it creates supersaturation fluctuations through local vertical velocity fluctuations, has the same artifacts as the much simpler stochastic eddy-hopping model. Hence, the broad DSD these DNS-like studies predict cannot be regarded as strictly local. Free of such inconsistencies are

other DNS studies (e.g., Paoli and Shariff 2009; Siewert et al. 2017; Saito et al. 2019), where supersaturation fluctuations are sustained by random scalar forcing applied on the largest scales of the computational box (supersaturation fluctuations at small scales are determined by downscale nonlinear transfer).

The eddy-hopping model can be used as a subgrid condensation scheme in LES (with particle-based microphysics) and tends to predict broad filtered DSD relative to the uniform condensation approximation. We emphasized in this work that actual local sampling of the filtered DSD must be enforced in LES by properly coupling the subgrid droplet transport with the subgrid vertical velocity fluctuations that cause subgrid supersaturation fluctuations.

Broader filtered DSD predicted by the eddy-hopping model may increase local (grid-averaged) condensation rates in LES compared with uniform condensation. However, broad filtered DSD does not necessarily imply enhanced probabilities of droplet collisions induced by differential sedimentation (as broad filtered DSD does not imply broad fine-grained DSD). Broader fine-grained DSD can be supported by the eddy-hopping model only through the condensation reversibility breaking that may occur at small scales on the order of the supersaturation relaxation length scale ℓ_s [see section 5 and the analysis of Clark and Hall (1979)]. This effect is more pronounced at the cloud base, where the supersaturation relaxation times τ_s (and the associated length ℓ_s) are sufficiently large. However, the filtered DSD $\langle n(r) \rangle_{\ell_s}$ with filter width $\sim \ell_s$ may be narrow in the cloud core (under the turbulent condensation represented by the eddy

hopping model) and cannot effectively enhance droplet collision probabilities.

a. Relation to cloud chamber experiments

Evidently, the eddy-hopping model (and the DNS-like models where S is driven by w) cannot explain the stationary DSD obtained from simulation data of the Pi chamber setup, as those reported and analyzed by Prabhakaran et al. (2022). The variability of the droplet growth conditions in the Pi chamber and in the idealized models considered here is attributed to different sources, operating on different spatial scales. In the Pi chamber [see, e.g., Chang et al. (2016)], the variability of the droplet growth conditions is caused by fixed scalar boundary conditions (for temperature and vapor on the chamber walls) that sustain supersaturation fluctuations against isobaric mixing due to Rayleigh–Bénard turbulence. Also, the domain of the Pi chamber is of relatively small vertical extent compared with typical grid boxes in LES. This rules out any significant variability in the adiabatic cooling rates among droplets (ascending with different turbulent vertical velocities), which is the main source of variability in the droplet growth conditions postulated by the models discussed in this work. Finally, we note that the turbulent condensation models discussed here assume the cloudy volume is effectively unbounded (although the DSD sampling volume is finite) and neglect droplet transport by sedimentation. The Pi chamber is a bounded system, where large droplets are removed by sedimentation from the sampling volume. This truncates the right tail of the sampled DSD, despite supersaturation fluctuations being continuously maintained by the boundary conditions.

b. Eddy-hopping model versus “real” eddy-hopping mechanism

This work indicates that the eddy-hopping model alone does not play a significant role in building up fine-grained DSDs that have the typical widths (of a few microns) observed in undiluted volumes of real clouds.

However, the term *eddy hopping* used here and throughout the text refers to the mere local variability of droplet growth conditions experiencing different adiabatic cooling rates due to vertical velocity fluctuations. It does not embody the *real* eddy-hopping mechanism in the sense of Cooper (1989), where droplets following different paths through a variable cloud microstructure [“hopping” different eddies as reviewed by Grabowski and Wang (2013)] experience different growth histories, thus causing the variance of droplet sizes reaching a given sampling volume in a cloud at a particular time.

Also, in a full cloud simulation of spatial resolution Δ , the eddy-hopping model (“eddy hopping” in the loose sense mentioned above) does not operate alone. Both filtered $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$ and fine-grained $\sigma_a^2(0)$ may be produced by other local mechanisms and, in addition, by the net flux of droplets of different sizes into a given grid box. This can be illustrated with the help of the balance equation for $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_a^2(\Delta)}{\partial t} = 4D \langle a'S' \rangle_\Delta - 4D \langle a'S'_{\text{eq}} \rangle_\Delta - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}, \quad (40)$$

where the first two terms on the rhs of (40) contribute to the *local* production rate of $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$. The term with the flux \mathbf{F} represents the net *transport* of $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$ due to droplet sedimentation and droplet advection by the cloud flow. For example, \mathbf{F} may bring to the sampling volume droplets that carry a memory of different growth histories experienced *outside* the sampling volume (nonlocal contribution to the real eddy hopping mechanism). In the Pi chamber case, \mathbf{F} accounts for the preferential removal of large droplets from the sampling volume. The second term in the rhs of (40) (where the equilibrium supersaturation S_{eq} incorporates the surface tension and solute effects) and the term involving \mathbf{F} were not treated in this work. They will be considered in future investigations.

The eddy-hopping model discussed here (operating as an SGS scheme with local sampling carefully enforced) directly computes (closes) the covariance $\langle a'S' \rangle_\Delta$ in (40). The supersaturation fluctuations S' are locally created (via the adiabatic cooling effect) by velocity fluctuations on a range of scales smaller or on the order of Δ (forcing of type A). Thus, the eddy-hopping model provides one simple mechanism for the *local production rate* of $\sigma_a^2(\Delta)$. As discussed in section 5, this mechanism may eventually produce nonnegligible fine-grained variance $\sigma_a^2(0)$ for sufficiently large values of the supersaturation relaxation time τ_s (occurring, for example, at the cloud base and in clouds of low CCN concentration).

Other mechanisms driving supersaturation fluctuations S' and contributing to $\langle a'S' \rangle_\Delta$ in (40) may be due to mean local gradients of the thermodynamic scalars interacting with SGS scalar fluxes or due to the net transport of scalar variance into the grid box. The latter situation is simulated in DNS-like studies of type B, where fluctuations of thermodynamic scalars are directly forced on a scale $\sim \Delta$. Then, the two types of forcing (A and B) considered in this work generally combine to create $\langle a'S' \rangle_\Delta$. The relative importance of each forcing type depends on the local conditions and on the configuration of the cloud flow.

The scale-dependent effects of droplet sedimentation (neglected here) suppress the production of supersaturation fluctuations via adiabatic cooling (thus mitigating the eddy hopping contribution to $\langle a'S' \rangle_\Delta$) and work to destroy correlations between droplet sizes and droplet vertical positions. A quantitative account of these effects poses several challenges to stochastic representations of turbulent condensation and is left for future investigations. The eddy-hopping model discussed in this work is then applicable to compute $\langle a'S' \rangle_\Delta$ in simulation grid boxes that contain droplets of small sizes, such as those occurring in the early stages of cloud development.

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Data availability statement. The data that support the findings of this study are available from the author upon reasonable request.

APPENDIX A

Reflection Algorithm

Here, we summarize the reflection algorithm of Wilson and Flesch (1993), which is one method of choice to enforce local DSD sampling (section 4b) while using the eddy-hopping model in the adiabatic cloud parcel (in the limit of reversible condensation).

Let $z(t)$ and $w(t)$ denote the position and velocity of a representative droplet at time t , with $z(t)$ in the sampling interval, that is, $z_B \leq z(t) \leq z_T$, with $z_T - z_B = \Delta$.

To obtain $z(t + \delta t)$ and $w(t + \delta t)$ after a time step δt , we first compute the provisional values z_* and w_* at time $t + \delta t$:

$$z_* = z(t) + \delta z, \quad w_* = w(t) + \delta w, \quad (\text{A1})$$

with finite increments δz and δw calculated according to

$$\delta z = w(t)\delta t, \quad \delta w = -\frac{w(t)}{\tau_w}\delta t + \sqrt{b}\delta W(t), \quad (\text{A2})$$

where $\delta W(t) = \xi(t)\sqrt{\delta t}$ and $\xi(t)$ has the Gaussian distribution with zero mean and unit variance. The coefficient b (Wilson and Flesch 1993) is

$$b = \frac{2\sigma_w^2}{\tau_w} \varphi(\delta t/\tau_w), \quad (\text{A3})$$

with modifying function

$$\varphi(\zeta) = \frac{1}{2\zeta} [1 - (1 - \zeta)^2], \quad \lim_{\zeta \rightarrow 0} \varphi(\zeta) = 1, \quad (\text{A4})$$

that approaches unity as $\zeta = \delta t/\tau_w$ becomes small enough.

The provisional state (z_*, w_*) may fall outside the sampling interval if $z_* < z_B$ or $z_* > z_T$. We then correct (z_*, w_*) for such disallowed state to obtain $[z(t + \delta t), w(t + \delta t)]$ in the sampling interval by using wall reflection at z_B and z_T according to the following algorithm (Wilson and Flesch 1993):

$$[z(t + \delta t), w(t + \delta t)] = \begin{cases} (2z_B - z_*, -w_*), & \text{if } z_* < z_B, \\ (2z_T - z_*, -w_*), & \text{if } z_* > z_T, \\ (z_*, w_*), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A5})$$

As shown in Wilson and Flesch (1993), the finite-increment model [(A1)–(A4)] with reflecting boundary conditions [(A5)] ensures that the tracer particles remain well mixed in the z – w space, with z uniformly distributed in $[z_B, z_T]$ and w having the Gaussian distribution.

In this work, we use a common time step δt to integrate the full set of models [(11)–(14)]. We choose δt sufficiently smaller than the shortest system time scale, which is the one required to resolve the droplet growth [(11)]. This choice implies $\delta t/\tau_w \ll 1$, yielding $\varphi \approx 1$ and b reduces to the usual value $2\sigma_w^2/\tau_w$ [see (13)] for infinitesimal time increment dt .

APPENDIX B

Modified Periodic Boundary Conditions

We sketch here a simple procedure to apply the modified PBC shown schematically in Fig. 4b. It restricts the droplet vertical position to the sampling interval $z_B \leq z \leq z_T$ (with $z_T - z_B = \Delta$) while preserving the mean vertical gradient $\bar{\gamma}_a$ of droplet squared radius. The scheme resembles the so-called Lees–Edwards boundary conditions (Lees and Edwards 1972) used in particle-based molecular dynamic simulations of fluids under shear flow.

Knowing the droplet vertical position $z(t)$ and its squared radius $a(t)$ at time t , we first obtain the provisional values z_* and a_* at time $t + \delta t$ by numerical integration of (14) and (7) over the model time step δt . Then, we correct (if necessary) the provisional values to obtain $z(t + \delta t)$ and $a(t + \delta t)$ as follows:

$$z(t + \delta t) = z_* + \epsilon \Delta \quad (\text{B1}) \text{ and}$$

$$a(t + \delta t) = a_* + \epsilon \gamma_a \Delta, \quad (\text{B2})$$

where

$$\epsilon = \begin{cases} +1, & \text{if } z_* < z_B, \\ -1, & \text{if } z_* > z_T, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B3})$$

which is the periodicity correction index and $\bar{\gamma}_a$ is the mean vertical gradient of the droplet squared radius.

For the eddy-hopping model operating in adiabatic parcels, we may assume that the vertical structure of a follows the quasisteady profile [(16)] over the length scale Δ of the sampling volume and approximate

$$\bar{\gamma}_a \approx 2DA_1\tau_s, \quad (\text{B4})$$

where the phase relaxation time τ_{ph} in τ_s is approximated as

$$\tau_{\text{ph}} \approx 1/[A_2 \langle \mu_1 \rangle_\Delta]. \quad (\text{B5})$$

For DNS-like models of type A, instead of using (B4) and (B5), $\bar{\gamma}_a$ may be estimated from a least squares fit to a linear profile of the droplet squared radius.

APPENDIX C

Phase Modification and Supersaturation Spectrum

The Fourier–Laplace transforms $S(\omega)$ and $w(\omega)$ of $S(t)$ and $w(t)$ are linearly related through the transfer function

$\varphi(\omega) = \varphi'(\omega) + i\varphi''(\omega)$ [(25)]. We write $\varphi'(\omega)$ and $\varphi''(\omega)$ in terms of reduced functions (Cichocki and Felderhof 1991) of the dimensionless frequency $\hat{\omega} = \omega\tau_s$:

$$R(\hat{\omega}) \equiv \frac{\varphi'(\hat{\omega})}{\varphi'(0)} = \frac{1}{1 + \hat{\omega}^2}, \quad I(\hat{\omega}) \equiv \frac{\varphi''(\hat{\omega})}{\varphi''(0)} = \frac{\hat{\omega}}{1 + \hat{\omega}^2}.$$

The reduced functions are plotted in Fig. C1. The real part $R(\hat{\omega})$, which is in phase with the “forcing” $w(t)$, dominates the “response” $S(t)$ in the lower frequency range ($\hat{\omega} = \omega\tau_s \lesssim 1$) but vanishes in the high-frequency regime ($\hat{\omega} \gtrsim 10$). The phase modification due to $I(\hat{\omega})$ takes place on a range of frequencies around $1/\tau_s$ (i.e., $\hat{\omega} = 1$).

Now, let us consider the power spectrum $E_s(\omega)$ of supersaturation fluctuations $S(t)$ driven by vertical velocity fluctuations $w(t)$. It can be shown that $E_s(\omega)$ is related to the power spectrum $E_w(\omega)$ of $w(t)$ through the transfer function $\varphi(\omega)$ defined in (25):

$$E_s(\omega) = |\varphi(\omega)|^2 E_w(\omega). \tag{C1}$$

The statistically stationary process $w(t)$ is described by (13) and has an autocorrelation function:

$$R_w(t) = \langle w'(t_0)w'(t_0 + t) \rangle = \sigma_w^2 e^{-t/\tau_w},$$

with integral time scale τ_w . The spectrum $E_w(\omega)$ is twice the Fourier transform of $R_w(t)$ [see, e.g., Pope (2000)] and equals

$$E_w(\omega) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R_w(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{\sigma_w^2 \tau_w}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_w^2}. \tag{C2}$$

Accordingly, $E_s(\omega)$ is twice the Fourier transform of $R_s(t) = \langle S'(t_0)S'(t_0 + t) \rangle$ with integral time scale τ_s . Then, it follows from (C1), (25), and (C2) that

FIG. C1. Reduced functions $R(\hat{\omega})$ and $I(\hat{\omega})$ as a function of the dimensionless frequency $\hat{\omega} = \omega\tau_s$.

$$E_s(\omega) = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{A_1^2 \tau_s^2}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_s^2} \frac{\sigma_w^2 \tau_w}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_w^2}.$$

The dimensionless spectrum $\hat{E}_s(\hat{\omega})$, scaled by $(2/\pi)A_1^2 \tau_s^2 \sigma_w^2 \tau_w$, in terms of the dimensionless frequency $\hat{\omega} = \omega\tau_s$ is

$$\hat{E}_s(\hat{\omega}) = \frac{1}{1 + \hat{\omega}^2} \frac{1}{1 + (\hat{\omega}/\alpha)^2}, \tag{C3}$$

where $\alpha = \tau_s/\tau_w$ is the ratio of the integral time scales of $S(t)$ and $w(t)$.

APPENDIX D

Equations for DNS-Like Models

In general, DNS studies of turbulent condensation solve the NS equations⁹ for the velocity field \mathbf{u} :

$$\partial_t \mathbf{u} = \dots + \mathbf{f}, \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \tag{D1}$$

where on the right-hand side (rhs) we omit the convective acceleration and the well-known NS terms, making explicit only the external statistically homogeneous and isotropic momentum forcing \mathbf{f} . It is applied on the larger scales $\sim \Delta$ of the computational box to maintain a turbulent stationary flow. This momentum forcing mimics turbulence production by scales larger than Δ and is a common feature of all DNS studies.

The treatment of thermodynamics and moisture, however, differs among various DNS studies. Some models resolve both the temperature T and the vapor mixing ratio q as the thermodynamic prognostic variables. The local changes in q and T are described by equations of the form

$$\partial_t q = f_q + \dots \tag{D2} \text{ and}$$

$$\partial_t T = -\Gamma w + f_T + \dots, \tag{D3}$$

where $\Gamma = g/c_p$ is the lapse rate accounting for the adiabatic cooling effect, $w = \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{e}}_z$ is the local vertical velocity, and f_q and f_T are the large-scale stochastic forcing of the vapor and temperature fields. The dots on the rhs of (D2) and (D3) represent other contributions, such as advection by the resolved turbulent field \mathbf{u} , molecular diffusion, and condensation (accompanied by latent heat exchanges). The local supersaturation S specifying the ambient conditions for droplet growth is diagnosed from T and q .

Other DNS studies do not resolve T or q but directly compute the supersaturation S driving droplet growth by condensation. In this S formulation for the thermodynamic scalars, the supersaturation obeys an equation of the form

$$\partial_t S = A_1 w + f_S + \dots, \tag{D4}$$

⁹ Some studies [e.g., Paoli and Shariff (2009)] solve the equations for compressible fluid motion. However, this feature is not relevant to the present discussion.

where f_S stands for the large-scale supersaturation forcing and A_1 is the coefficient [same as in (4)] accounting for the adiabatic cooling effect. Again, the dots on the rhs of (D4) represent turbulent advection by \mathbf{u} , molecular diffusion, and condensation. The rhs of the equations above for T , q , and S makes explicit only the “external” stochastic sources producing fluctuations in the thermodynamic scalars (other than small-scale fluctuations due to the nonlinear cascade) that lead to variability in droplet growth conditions.

DNS studies of type B neglect the adiabatic cooling effect by assuming $\Gamma = 0$ (or $A_1 = 0$ in the S formulation) and simulate supersaturation fluctuations solely produced by the scalar forcing at large scales $\sim \Delta$; hence, they assume $f_T \neq 0$ and $f_q \neq 0$ in (D3) and (D2) [or $f_S \neq 0$ in the S formulation (D4)].

DNS studies of type A do not apply any large-scale scalar forcing. Hence, they assume $f_T = f_q = 0$ in (D3) and (D2) [or $f_S = 0$ in (D4)] and rely on the local adiabatic cooling effect driven by vertical velocity fluctuations ($\Gamma \neq 0$ or $A_1 \neq 0$) as the only source of supersaturation variability.

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